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Exercise Habit and Body Composition of Staff of Kogi State College of Education (Technical) Kabba, Kogi State, Nigeria

Donatus CHUKWUDO ¹ and Dare Michael ENIETAN ²

¹ Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka

² Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education, Kogi State College of Education (Technical) Kabba, Kogi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study was designed to investigate the body composition as well as the exercise habit of the staff of Kogi State College of Education (Technical), Kabba, Kogi State, Nigeria. Three research questions were asked with three hypotheses tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The study's population consisted of 505 employees of KSCOE (T), Kabba Kogi State, and the design was a cross-sectional survey. A sample of 153 people was populated without modification using a simple voting system. The researchers collected data using behavioral surveys. The device was validated by five experts from the Department of Human Kinetics and Health Studies, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. The reliability of the scale was determined using Cronbach Alpha's formula. Research questions were answered using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. The null hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Variance ANOVA at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that both

male and female staff were overweight; both male and female staff were with normal waist to hip ratio (WHR); and male staff were with normal body fat percentage, but female staff members were with abnormal body fat percentage. Male exercisers were with normal WHR while male's non-exercisers were with abnormal WHR and body fat percent. Female exercisers were with normal WHR while female non-exercisers were with abnormal WHR and body fat percentage. This study recommended that regular exercise habit should be encouraged and similar study on the effects of exercise should be conducted among staff in the same location or different locations in any part of Nigeria.

Keywords: Health Education, Exercise Habit, Body Composition, Waist to Hip Ratio, Body Fat, Staff Health

Introduction

The body composition of people all over the world is giving concern to experts and researchers in the field of Exercise and Health. A lot of people inaccurately assume that they are not in control of their body composition. They often adopt unhealthy lifestyles which are thought to lead to weight gain. On average, workers gain about 1.4 kg - 2.3 kg during their first to five years of working, (Lee & Lee, 2021). However, little is known about how body composition changes. Certainly, there are genetics in play to some degree. But many people lean on that and use it as an excuse for their state of body composition. One's body composition is very heavily impacted by what one eats and how one exercises. That means that one can be in control of body composition. Generally, the body is made up of lean mass, including muscles and organs, and fat mass, these together are commonly referred to as body composition.

Globally, obesity has nearly tripled since 1975. In 2016, more than 1.9 billion adults, 18 years and older, were overweight. Of these over 650 million were obese. 39% of adults aged 18 years and over were overweight in 2016, and 13% were obese. Over 340 million children and adolescents aged 5-19 were obese in 2016. Most of the world's population lives in countries where obesity kills more people than underweight (WHO, 2018). In 2016, 39% men and 39% of women aged 18+ were overweight ($BMI \geq 25 \text{ kg/m}^2$) and 11% of men and 15% of women were obese ($BMI \geq 30 \text{ kg/m}^2$). Thus, nearly 2 billion adults worldwide were overweight and, of these, more than half a billion were obese. Obesity has shown a marked increase over the past 4 decades. Obesity rates in men have risen from around 3% in 1975 and in women from just over 6% in 1975 while overweight has risen over this same time period from 20% in men and from just under 23% in women (WHO, 2018).

The prevalence of obesity was highest in the WHO regions of the Americas (62% for overweight in both sexes, and 26% for obesity) and lowest in the WHO region for Southeast Asia (14% overweight in both sexes and 3% for obesity). In all WHO regions women were more likely to be obese than men. In the WHO regions for Africa, Eastern Mediterranean and Southeast Asia, women had roughly double the obesity prevalence of men (WHO, 2018). Worldwide, at least 2.8 million people die each year as a result of being overweight or obese, and an estimated 35.8 million (2.3%) of global DALYs are caused by overweight or obesity. Overweight and obesity lead to adverse metabolic effects on blood pressure, cholesterol, triglycerides and insulin resistance (WHO, 2018). The increment in

obese individuals can be easily seen by comparing data of 2015 and 2016 when 38.7% of adult females were obese worldwide which increased to 39.2% in 2016 and 38.0% of adult males were obese worldwide which increased to 38.5% in 2016 (WHO, 2017). In 1995 and 2000, 200 million obese adults were found worldwide, which increased to over 300 million in 2000 and now in 2016 it has reached 600 million (WHO, 2018).

In Africa, the burden of obesity and overweight prevalence has increased significantly over the last two decades (Ozodiegwu, Littleton, Nwabueze, Famojuro, Quinn, Wallace, et al. 2019). Among sub-Saharan African women, the prevalence of obesity increased by 12% between 1975 and 2016, while the prevalence of overweight increased by 24% (Tydeman, Van-Rooyen & Walsh, 2018). Among men, obesity prevalence increased by 5%, while overweight prevalence increased by 15% in the same period (Neupane, Prakash & Doku. 2016). The authors asserted that there has been an increased intake of energy-dense foods that are high in fat.

In Nigeria, the prevalence of obesity was 11 per cent and 15 per cent among men and woman (WHO, 2018). A literature review and meta-analysis conducted in Nigeria indicated a rising trend of overweight (26.0%) and obesity (15.0%) over the years. The prevalence of obesity in the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria indicates the following: Southeast 29.3 per cent, Southwest 13.9 per cent, South-south 24.7 per cent, Northwest 10.4 per cent, North-central 10.2 per cent, and North-east 6.4 per cent (Chukwuonye *et al.*, 2022).

The prevalence of overweight and obesity in the 6 geopolitical zones of Nigeria was reported by Chuwuonye *et al.* (2022), that in North-central overweight and obesity was 25.3per cent and 10.2per cent respectively, in which Kogi State was included. A study conducted by Zileli *et al.* (2016) asserted that lack of regular exercise has been identified as a major cause of obesity. Increasing use of motorized transport and sedentary types of occupation such as office work, accompanied by high-risk dietary and lifestyle/behaviors were associated with the prevalence of obesity. Therefore, this present study seeks to assess the effect of a twelve-week brisk walking on body composition of obese female adults in Kogi State, Nigeria

Body composition is a component of health-related fitness used to describe the percentage of fat, bone, water and muscle in the body expressed as percent body mass, visceral fat and lean muscle mass (Ibrahim & Akram, 2021). The authors also asserted that excessive body fat is associated with increased metabolic risk and its measurement is important in implementing curative and preventive health measures. Body Composition is a physical measurement that provides more specific information about body make-up than body weight alone. Body composition is defined as the proportion of fat and fat free mass (FFM) in the body (Safaei, Sundararajan, Driss, Booulila, & Shapi, 2021). Fat free mass includes primarily muscles, bone and water along with some other elements. Fat mass includes fat that is stored as an energy source and fat in the central nervous system, organs, bone marrow and sex tissues, known as essential fat and non-essential fats (Safaei *et al.*, 2021). Body composition is one of the five components of health-related fitness. It is determined by comparing the body fat mass to its fat-free mass (bone, muscles and other tissues). Body composition is used to describe the percentages of fat, bone, water and muscle in the body.

Body composition is the measurement of the human body in terms of its dimensions of bone, muscle and adipose (fat) tissue. The field of body composition encompasses a variety of human body measurements. Height, stature (standing height), recumbent length, skinfold thickness, circumference (head, waist, limb lengths, and breadths (shoulder, wrist and so on) are examples of anthropometric measures. Body composition connotes the percentage of fat, bone, water, and muscle in the body (Powell-Wiley *et al.*, 2021). Two types of same sex and body weight may look completely different from each other because they have a different body composition, (Powell-Wiley *et al.*, 2021). Percentage body fat (PBF) is total mass of fat divided by total body mass; and that includes essential body fat and storage body fat (Powell-Wiley *et al.*, 2021). Essential body fat is necessary to maintain life and productive functions. The percentage of essential body fat for women is greater than that of men, due to the demands of childbearing and other hormonal functions (Devi, Nilupher, Gupta, Dhall & Kapoor, 2020). The percentage of essential fat is 3-5per cent in men (Shweta, 2019). Storage body fat consists of fat accumulation in adipose tissue, part of which protects internal organs in the chest and abdomen.

There are regular exercisers (5-6 times a week), occasional exercisers (occasionally participating in exercise), and sedentary people (those who do not always exercise). In other words, when the behavior is repeated, people do not need to weigh the pros and cons or analyze their actions and behaviors to make choices. The subsequent behavior may be an emotional one and often results from specific events that precede it. Behavior can be defined as the active development of the desire to participate in regular sports.

Attitudes are habits towards participating in exercise. Where a person participates in sports will determine their body composition. Exercise habits may change; we have daily workouts, weekly workouts, monthly workouts, occasional workouts, and no workouts. This exercise group will be tested with questions regarding the impact of physical exercise on the staff of KSCOET, Kabba.

Compared to weight, body composition can be more precisely determined by physical measurements. Body composition is defined as the ratio of body fat to fat-free mass (FFM) (Malema, 2021). Lean meat consists mostly of meat, bones, and water, along with a few other ingredients. Fats include essential fats, called essential and non-essential fats, which are stored as energy and fat in the central nervous system, muscles, bones, and sexual tissues (Malema, 2021). Body composition is one of the five factors related to health. It is determined by comparing the body's fat content with its fat-free content (bones, muscles, and other tissues). Body composition is used to describe the percentage of fat, bone, water and muscle in the body.

This research aimed to establish the differences and connection linking body composition and body somatotype of staff of KSCOET (Tech), Kabba, based on exercise habit, and encourage regular exercise to maintain good and healthy body composition.

Statement of the Problem

Research shows that there is an increase in the risk of chronic diseases like coronary heart disease (CHD), stroke, osteoporosis, diabetes, obesity and hypertension which have become the leading causes of morbidity and mortality, due to inadequate and poor exercise habits.

In the light of this present situation, the fitness and health of staff of KSCOET (Tech) Kabba is at stake if exercise habits are not formed. It is worrisome for the researchers to observe that there is a high rate of excess weight and body build, people have a negative attitude towards exercise and do not understand the values of exercise. Research work has been carried out on the body composition of athletes, especially in relation to sport performance but little in relation to exercise habits and body composition, particularly for workers' health. This motivated the researchers to investigate exercise habits and body composition of staff of KSCOET (Tech) Kabba, Kogi State, Nigeria.

Research Objectives

Specifically, this study ascertained the:

- i. body composition (height, BMI, fat percentage, hip circumference, waist circumference) of staff of KSCOET, Kabba;
- ii. body composition (height, BMI, fat percentage, hip circumference, waist circumference) of male staff of KSCOET, Kabba, based on exercise habit; and
- iii. body composition of female staff of KSCOET, Kabba based on exercise habit.

Research Questions

The following study questions have been posed to guide the research.

- i. What is the body composition of staff of KSCOET, Kabba?
- ii. What is the body composition of male staff of KSCOET, Kabba, based on exercise habit?
- iii. There is no significant difference in Body Fat Percentage (Fat%) of staff of KSCOET (Tech), Kabba, based on exercise habit.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested for the purpose of this study:

- i. There is no important distinction in Body Mass Index (BMI) of staff of KSCOET (Tech), Kabba, based on exercise habit.
- ii. There is no important distinction in Waist to Hip Ratio (WHR) of staff of KSCOET (Tech), Kabba, based on exercise habit.
- iii. There is no significant difference in body composition of female staff of KSCOET (Tech), Kabba, based on exercise habit.

Methodology

This study used a cross-sectional survey research design. The research was carried out at Kogi State College of Education (Technical), Kabba, located at kilometer 6 on Kabba-Okene highway in Western part of Kogi State, Nigeria. The college is in operation at Gbeleko and Egbeda in Kabba/Bunu Local Government for academic and administrative activities. Presently, there are 4 academic schools namely School of Sciences, School of Vocational Education, School of Technical Education and School of Education and 3 Administrative Departments.

All academic and non-academic employees of Kogi State College of Education (Technical) Kabba served as the study's population. According to the internal memorandum

released by staff support services in 2019, there are 505 staff in the college. The academic staff is 88, and the non-academic staff is 417, giving a total of 505 staff.

The sample for the study consists of 153 staff which is 25per cent of the population (academic staff and non-academic staff) of KSCOE (Tech) Kabba. This is in line with the suggestion of Cohen, Manion & Morrison (2017) that, population of 7, 000 and above 5% should be used, for population of 5, 000, 10 per cent should be used, for population of 1, 000, 20 per cent should be used, and population that is less than 1000, 23 to 25per cent should be used. Nine (9) staff (teaching and non-teaching staff) was sampled from each department, making a total of 153 staff, using simple random sampling techniques of balloting without replacement.

A structured questionnaire developed by the study's researchers on exercise habits was used to collect information on exercise habits. The questionnaire comprises two sections, A and B. Section A focused on respondents' socio-demographic variables; Section B focused on exercise habits of staff of KSCOE (Tech), Kabba. In section B, 21 items asked questions for information on exercise habit with response options of YES or NO. Laboratory weighing scale model EF921 Japan was used to measure body mass in kilogram (Kg). Measuring Tape (The butterfly trademark 758ae U.S.A, non-elastic tape) graduated in centimeters was used for measuring hip circumference, waist circumference, wrist circumference. Skinfold caliper (model HNR-22 Littman's caliper) was used to determine the body fat in sites identified in millimeter (mm).

The University of Nigeria Nsukka's Head of the Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education provided the researcher with an introduction letter. The provost of the college received that letter of introduction and approved the staff's participation in the study.

Data for this study were gathered using a standardized questionnaire designed by the researchers regarding exercise habits. Three assistants were utilized by the researchers to administer and gather the questionnaire. In order to gather the staff's complete questionnaire and begin the measurement, the researchers and assistant waited for them to finish.

The measurement on body composition, was carried out in the school (KSCOE, (Tech), Kabba) sports ground and exercise physiology laboratory immediately after the response to the questionnaire. The following body measurements were measured: BMI, fat%, waist circumference, hip circumference and wrist circumference. The period of measurement, in accordance with WHO (2002) recommendation, the measurements was in the morning when the subjects had not taken anything solid or liquid as food.

Version 20 of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to code, sort, and analyze the collected data. To evaluate the gathered data, descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used. Hypotheses were tested using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level of significant. Pearson Correlation Coefficient was used to analyse the effect of gender on body composition.

Formulae:

$$\text{Body Mass Index (BMI)} = \frac{\text{Weight}}{\text{Height}^2} = \frac{W(\text{kg})}{h^2(\text{m})}$$

$$\text{Waist to Hip Ratio (WHR)} = \frac{\text{waist circumference}}{\text{Hip circumference}} = \frac{W}{h}$$

Fat % for male = 0.1051 x (sum of parts of the body measure) + 2.585,

Fat % female = 0.1545 x (sum of parts of the body measure) + 3.580

(Source: Values for obesity judgment proposed by WHO, 2002).

Results

Results of the study are presented according to the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question One

What is the body composition of staff of KSCOET, Kabba?

Table 1: Summary of descriptive statistics of Body Composition (BMI, WHR and Fat %). Staff of KSCOET (Tech), Kabba

Body mass index				
(kg/m ²)	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
Male	82	26.7366	4.57287	Overweight
Female	68	27.6853	4.81326	Overweight
Waist to Hip Ratio				
Male	82	.8548	.05248	Normal
Female	68	.8182	.05588	Normal
Fat Percentage (%)				
Male	82	14.1090	4.25180	Normal
Female	68	23.8606	7.42066	Abnormal

Table 1 shows the male BMI as mean 26.7366 with standard deviation of 4.5728, Hip to Waist Ratio (WHR) mean .8548 with standard deviations of .05248 and Fat Percentage (Fat %) mean 14.1090 with standard deviation of 4.25180. The table further shows that, female BMI as mean 27.6853 with standard deviation of 4.81326, Hip to Waist Ratio (WHR) mean .8182 with standard deviation of .05588, and body Fat Percentage (Fat %) mean 23.8606 with standard deviation of 7.42066. It implies that both male and female are overweight, both male and female are with normal waist to hip ratio, male with normal fat % and female with abnormal fat%.

Research Question Two

What is the body composition of male staff of KSCOET, Kabba, based on exercise habit?

Table 2: Summary of descriptive statistic of body composition (BMI, WHR and Fat %) of male staff of KSCOET (Tech), Kabba, based on exercise habit

Category Exercise habit	N	BMI		
		Mean(kg/m ²)	Std. deviation	Decision
Non exercisers	10	27.4770	4.78665	Overweight
Occasional exercisers	31	26.6266	4.51590	Overweight
Regular exercisers	41	26.6573	4.66233	Overweight
		WHR		
Non exercisers	10	.8460	.04452	Normal
Occasional exercisers	31	.8590	.04556	Normal
Regular exercisers	41	.8537	.05949	Normal
		Fat%		
Non exercisers	10	16.7080	6.42258	Normal
Occasional exercisers	31	13.2439	3.86857	Normal
Regular exercisers	41	14.1293	3.71925	Normal

Table 2 shows the male body composition (BMI, WHR and Fat %) based on exercise habit. The male non-exerciser's BMI are (mean=27.4770, SD=4.78665), non-exerciser's WHR are (mean=.8460 SD=.04452) and non-exerciser's Fat% are (mean=16.7080 SD=6.42258). Occasional exerciser's BMI are (mean=26.60266, SD=4.51590), occasional exerciser's WHR are (mean=.8590, SD=.04556) and occasional exerciser's Fat% are (mean=13.2439, SD=3.86857). Regular exerciser's BMI are (mean=26.6573, SD=4.66233), regular exerciser's WHR are (mean=.8537, SD=.05949) and regular exerciser's Fat% are (mean=14.1293, SD=3.71925). It implies that all the male exercisers are overweight, all the male exercisers are with normal WHR and all the male exercisers are with normal fat%.

Research Question Three

What is body composition of female staff KSCOET, Kabba, based on exercise habit?

Table 3: Summary of descriptive statistic of body composition (BMI, WHR and Fat %) of female staff of KSCOET (Tech), Kabba, based on exercise habit.

Exercise habit	N	BMI		
		Mean (kg/m ²)	Std. deviation	Decision
Non exercisers	19	29.8911	5.49218	Overweight
Occasional exercisers	27	27.5004	4.51822	Overweight
Regular exercisers	22	26/0073	3.92296	Overweight
		WHR (cm)		
Non exercisers	19	.7979	.05912	Normal
Occasional exercisers	27	.8215	.05475	Normal
Regular exercisers	22	.8318	.05170	Normal
		Fat%		
Non exercisers	19	31.8842	2.99332	Abnormal
Occasional exercisers	27	21.0515.	5.30219	Normal

Regular exercisers	22	20.3786	7.21783	Normal
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Table 3 shows the female body composition (BMI, WHR and Fat %) based on exercise habit. The non-exerciser’s BMI are (mean=29.8911, SD=5.49218), non-exerciser’s WHR are (mean=.7979, SD=.05912) and non-exerciser’s Fat% are (mean=31.8842, SD=2.99332). Occasional exerciser’s BMI are (mean=27.5004, SD=4.51822), occasional exerciser’s WHR are (mean=.8215, SD=.05475) and occasional exerciser’s Fat% are (mean=21.0515, SD=5.30291). Regular exerciser’s BMI are (mean=26.0073, SD=3.92296), regular exerciser’s WHR are (mean=.8318, SD=.05170) and regular exerciser’s Fat% are (mean=20.3786, SD=7.21783). It implies that all the female exercisers are overweight, all the male exercisers are with normal WHR, occasional and regular exercisers are with normal Fat% while non-exercisers are having abnormal Fat%.

Table 4: Correlations of male body composition and exercise habit of staff of KSCOE (Tech), Kabba

Items	N	Correlation value (r)	P-value	Decision
Male				
Exercise habit	82	.713	-.041	Weak relationship
Body Mass Index	82	.713	-.041	Weak relationship
Exercise habit	82	.898	.014	Weak relationship
Waist to Hip Ratio	82	.898	.014	Weak relationship
Exercise habit	82	.348	-.105	Weak relationship
Fat percentage (Fat%)	82	.348	-.102	Weak relationship

Table 4 shows that the male correlation value of BMI ($r = -.713$, $p = -.041$), WHR ($r = .898$, $p = -.014$), and FAT% ($r = .348$, $p = -.105$) at 0.05 level of significance. This mean that the body composition of the male staff has weak relationship with exercise habit as the p values are less than 0.05 degree of significance. Impliedly, body composition is not correlated with exercise habit of male staff.

Research Hypothesis One

There is no important distinction in Body Mass Index (BMI) of staff of KSCOE (Tech), Kabba, based on exercise habit.

Table 5: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for Body Mass Index (BMI) of staff of KSCOE (Tech), Kabba, based on exercise habit.

Body Mass Index (BMI)		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Male	Within Classifications	6.296	2	3.148	.147	.863
	Within Groups	1687.504	79	21.361		
	Total	1693.800	81			
Female	Between Groups	155.312	2	77.656	3.613	.033
	Within Groups	1396.908	65	21.491		
	Total	1552.220	67			

The computed F value and matching BMI P value for males ($F=.147, P=.863>0.05$) are displayed in Table 5. The null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the maximum body weight assessed by Pointing, is not valid because the significance of the P value between 2 and 79 degrees of freedom is greater than 0.05. The computed F value and corresponding BMI P value for females ($F=3.613, P=0.033<0.05$) are also displayed in the table. The null hypothesis, according to which there is no significant difference in behavioural assessments of maximum physical parameters, can be accepted because a P value of less than 0.05 is significant between 2 and 65 degrees of freedom. Given that the p value is more than 0.05, it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in male BMI based on exercise behaviour, while there is a significant difference in female BMI based on exercise behaviour.

Research Hypothesis Two

There is no important distinction in Waist to Hip Ratio (WHR) of staff of KCOE (Tech), Kabba, based on exercise habit.

Table 6: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for Waist to Hip Ratio (WHR) of staff of KSCOE (Tech), Kabba, based on exercise habit.

Waist to hip ratio (WHR)		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Male	Within Classifications	.001	2	.001	.246	.782
	Within Classifications	.222	79	.003		
	Total	.223	81			
Female	Within Classifications	.012	2	.006	2.014	.142
	Within Classifications	.197	65	.003		
	Total	.209	67			

Table 6 shows male P values and corresponding waist-hip ratio P values ($F = 0.246, P = 0.782 > 0.05$). Since the degrees of freedom are 2 and 67, the P value is above the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in body composition according to application was not rejected. The supplementary table shows the P value of women and their corresponding P value of waist-hip ratio ($F = 2.014, P = 0.142 > 0.05$). Since the P value is greater than 0.05, the important level is between 2 and 65 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there was no important difference in waist-to-hip ratio (WHR) due to exercise behavior was rejected. This means that the waist-to-waist ratio of men and women is not different according to the application, because the P value is greater than the 0.05 significance level.

Research Hypothesis Three

There is no significant difference in Body Fat Percentage (Fat%) of staff of KCOE(Tech), Kabba, based on exercise habit.

Table 7: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for of Body Fat Percentage (Fat%) staff of KSCOE (Tech), Kabba, based on exercise habit

Waist to hip ratio (WHR)		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Fat% Male	Between Groups	90.767	2	45.383	2.610	.080
	Within Groups	1373.533	79	17.386		
	Total	1464.300	81			
Fat% Female	Between Groups	1702.979	2	851.489	27.862	.000
	Within Groups	1986.460	65	30.561		
	Total	3689.439	67			

Table 7 shows the calculated F value and corresponding body fat percentage P for men ($F = 2.610$, $P = 0.080 > 0.05$). Since P values are greater than 0.05 levels of significance and 2 to 67 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in body fat percentage (Fat%) will not be held in practice. The supplementary table shows the P value for women and the P value equal to body fat percentage ($F = 27.862$, $P = 0.000 < 0.05$). Because the P value between 2 and 65 degrees of freedom is greater than the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in body fat percentage in exercise behavior is rejected. Women do not differ by behaviour.

Discussion

The discoveries of this research in Table 1 indicated that both male and female are overweight, both male and female are with normal waist to hip ratio (WHR), male with normal fat % and female with abnormal fat%. This discovery was stunning and unforeseen because individuals are expected to have different body weight, WHR and Fat%. This finding was in contrast with Ghazali and Sanusi (2010), who reported that her respondents possessed different body composition. However, this finding is also consistent with that of Patil & Rajaram (2015), who reported that body composition differed. This implies that the indices of body composition (BMI, WHR and Fat %) should be checked regularly to maintain normal body composition.

The finding of this study in Table 2 indicated that all the male exercisers are overweight, all the male exercisers are with normal WHR and all the male exercisers are with normal fat%. This discovery was stunning and unforeseen for all the male exercisers to be overweight. This finding was in contrast with Bojan (2011), who reported that exercise determined body weight. This finding was also in contrast with Ghazali & Sanusi, (2010), who reported that exercise served as a key to determining body weight. This implies that the body weight was as a result of muscle mass but not overfat.

The finding of this study in Table 3 indicated that all the female exercisers are overweight with normal WHR, occasional and regular exercisers are with normal Fat%, while non-exercisers are having abnormal Fat%. This finding was not surprising and expected for all the female non-exercisers to be overweight and over fat. This finding was consistent with that of Bojan (2011), who reported that exercise determined body weight. The finding is also consistent with that of Sangmo & Hong (2011), who reported that exercise determined body composition. This implies that exercise determines body composition therefore exercise should be encouraged to be done regularly.

The findings of this study in Table 4 projects the relationship in body composition of staff of KSCOE (Tech) Kabba and exercise habit. The body composition of the male staff had weak relationship with exercise habit as the p values are lower than 0.05 level of importance. This finding was surprising and not expected. This is because exercise habits are supposed to have relationship with body composition. This finding was in contrast with that of Rita & Morassut (2018), who reported that body composition and exercise habits were related, but in agreement with Diego (2014), who reported that exercise does not determine body composition. Which mean that, the males' categories of body composition and exercisers habit did not differ.

The finding of this study in table 5 shows the difference in male BMI based on exercise habit (regular exercisers, occasional exercisers and non-exercisers). the male BMI not differed according to exercise habits since the p value was greater than 0,05 level of importance while female BMI differed according to exercise habit, since the P-value was less than .05 level of significance. This finding was surprising especially in male BMI because it is expected that BMI should be differed based on exercise habit. This finding is in contrast to Yamamoto (2009), who reported that exercise habit influences mass index. It is also in contrast with that of David, Tomlinson, Waller, Miller Naglieri (2007), who reported that regular exercise determined the body mass index. Therefore, the staff overweight may be as a result of muscle weight and not overfat.

The finding of this study in Table 6 shows the difference in both male and female WHR based on exercise habit (regular exercisers, occasional exercisers and non-exercisers). Both male and female WHR are not differed based on exercise habit since their P values were higher than .05 level of significance. This finding was not surprising because of the fact that individuals with regular exercise will have normal and WHR. This finding is, however, consistent with that of Patil & Rajaram (2015), who reported that WHR and exercise habit were differed and also consistent with the finding by Yamamoto (2009), who reported that lifestyle and body and exercise habit determined WHR. Therefore, the staff are with normal WHR and excise habit should be encouraged to maintain WHR.

The finding of this study in Table 8 shows the difference in both male and female Fat% based on exercise habit (regular exercisers, occasional exercisers and non-exercisers). The male Body Fat% did not differ based on exercise habit since their P-value were greater than .05 level of significance, while the female Body Fat% differed based on exercise habit since the P values were greater than .05 level of significance. This discovery was unforeseen and stunning because it is expected that exercise should influence the body fat%. This finding was in contrast with that of Sangmo & Hong (2011), who reported that exercise

determined body fat. The finding was also in contrast with that of American Council on Exercise – ACE (2009), who reported that lifestyle and exercise habit determined and influence body fat%. Therefore, the staff overweight may be as a result of muscle weight and not overfat.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions could be put together. The majority of the males were regular exercisers while majority of the female were occasional exercisers, the majority of the staff were overweight but not overfat. The male non exercisers, occasional exercisers and regular exercisers were overweight with moderate WHR and moderate body fat % based on exercise habit. Female non exercisers were obese, some of occasional exercisers were over fat and overweight, regular exercisers were overweight with moderate WHR and moderate Fat % based on exercise habit. Regular body measurement is to be practiced in Kogi State College of Education (Technical) and other institutions for the staff members to have desired good body composition. There is no significant difference in the body composition of male and female staff members due to regular exercise practice. There were reductions in the body weight, body mass index (BMI), Waist -Hip ratio and fat percentage of the KSCOET (T) staff members as a result of regular exercise.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, discussion and conclusion of the study, the following propositions were put together:

- i. The college, KSCOET (Tech) Kabba, should make exercise mandatory during the hour of college games and sports for all the staff, which can encourage exercise habits.
- ii. There should be regular body measurement to know the staff's body compositions.
- iii. The national commission for colleges of education stipulated sports schedules as reflected on the academic lecture timetable should be made compulsory for all the staff to encourage exercise habits.
- iv. The college management should ensure availability of sport equipment and facilities in the college to promote sport participation and to encourage and build staff exercise habit

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